

Notes on Confirmation Documents

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1 Preamble

This guidance document sets out *one* way of thinking about Confirmation Documents. As a supervisor who semi-regularly provides feedback on draft Confirmation Documents, I have become aware that many people seem to submit first drafts with similar shortcomings. I write this document in the hope that some of those common pitfalls can be avoided through the provision of early, clear guidance—thereby saving time and effort for both supervisee and supervisor. It is important to note that, by writing and circulating this document, I do not mean to imply that there is one formulaic way in which all Confirmation Documents must be written. Considerable variation is indeed possible between Confirmation Documents because there is considerable variation between PhD projects! But I do hope that the suggested structure will be helpful in many cases, especially where you find yourself staring at a blank screen when considering a particular document section, with inspiration lacking. I do assert that in all cases you will need to think about the *kinds of issues* that are raised in this document even if, in the end, the way you choose to address those issues is different from the way that I suggest.

The initial points to consider are these:

- Confirmation Documents have relatively tight word count restrictions. My suggestion is to map out the structure of your document early in the process and allocate to yourself a word limit for each section—and then stick to it! You should be aware that your document is essentially *setting out and justifying* a research plan, and content should be prioritised for inclusion on that basis. The Confirmation Document is not a draft thesis! A very common issue of “front-heaviness” occurs where an author spends too long setting out very general information at the start of their document, or fails to prioritise content in early sections, and tries to compensate by making later sections disproportionately terse so as to remain within the wordcount. *We have all been there at some time or other*, and the resulting re-drafting process can be painful and arduous. Please avoid this scenario wherever possible.
- The criteria used by the panel to assess your submission are reproduced in Fig. 1 below:

Figure 1: Panel assessment criteria for Confirmation Documents

- This document aims to guide you in producing a Confirmation Document that will meet these criteria.
- The second criterion, which refers to the Lancaster University Manual of Academic Regulations and Procedures (MARP), is relatively opaque. Having looked at the MARP some time ago, in my view the only key point for Confirmation Documents that is not covered in the *other* bullet points relates to your *awareness of the potential limitations of your research project*.
- Most of the other criteria are self-explanatory, though it can be instructive to scrutinise the actual wording—

do consider and take on board the meaning of phrases such as “know (of)”, “selected”, “chosen”, “appropriate”, and “realistic”.

2 Abstract

Providing an Abstract is not, strictly speaking, *compulsory* when writing a Confirmation Document, but I do recommend doing so. Abstracts are useful for readers, while writing one is, I contend, a useful exercise for you since it forces you to summarise what the main point of your project actually is. In fact, I would advise writing an Abstract at least *twice*. My suggestion is to write an Abstract as the first thing you do when approaching the Confirmation Document, for the purposes of self-clarification. As you write the document your ideas will no doubt start to change somewhat. I would therefore suggest discarding the initial Abstract once the rest of the document reaches an advanced stage, and then writing a second version that you will present to the reader.

This book, which is available online via MyiLibrary, provides a useful overview of academic Abstracts, in section 2.3:

Hartley, J. (2008). *Academic writing and publishing: A practical handbook*. Oxon: Routledge.

In particular, Hartley advocates writing Abstracts in a manner that somewhat reflects how Abstracts tend to be structured in medical and natural science research articles. I reproduce two of Hartley's suggested structures in Fig. 2 below.

Figure 2: Potential structures for academic abstracts. Reproduced from Hartley (2008).

My recommendation is to choose one of the two models in Fig. 2, to use that model as a template for writing the Abstract, and then to remove the headings at the end prior to presenting your text to a reader. Clearly, you will not have *Results* or *Conclusions* to report at this early stage of your project. My recommendation would be to discuss the *kinds* of results and/or conclusions you hope to produce from your project, and to suggest how those results and/or conclusions would contribute to the area of debate you discuss in the *Background* section. In other words, the questions posed are: to which named research fields¹ will your work contribute, and what is the nature of the contribution you are hoping to make?

3 Introduction section

The purpose of an Introduction section is to set out a brief overview of your project. By unspoken convention, the

¹ Examples might include “the literature on organisational change in higher education”, “the Computer Supported Collaborative Learning field”, “the body of work on Networked Learning in ASEAN countries”, “debates on pre-service teacher education”, etc.

Introduction will be written *as though the Abstract does not exist*, rather than as a continuation of it; this means that you might well re-state some of the content of the Abstract, though it is considered bad form to reproduce text from the Abstract exactly. This is an exceptional case to consider when structuring your document, because in most other cases you *will* want each section to directly build on what went before it.

The Introduction will mention the context, your approach, and your research questions, and indicate how the remainder of the document will be structured. I will say something about each of these matters in turn in what follows. I shall encapsulate each of those topics within its own subsection, though my doing so is *not* meant to imply that you must reproduce that subsection structure in your Confirmation document unnecessarily.

3.1 Context

There are a number of different focus points that I am grouping together here under this heading of Context. The relative weight given to each focus point, and the order in which you present them to the reader, will vary between Confirmation Documents. However, I do think that when writing an Introduction section you should consider saying something about:

- *The areas of research literature that you are drawing from, and to which you are hoping to contribute.* Clearly, you are not writing your actual *literature review* here². Nonetheless, it is typically a priority to establish from the start that your piece of research has a good chance of contributing to a particular research community or debate to some extent. You might highlight a gap in the existing literature, for example, or consider the differences between prior work and what your project sets out to accomplish. The aim at *this* moment in your narrative is to identify why a *research* audience might be interested in reading your work, as opposed to institutional, policymaker and/or practitioner audiences.
- *The context of policy and changes in policy.* Depending on your project, the policies you draw on might be governmental, global, international, national, regional, or institutional. They might be derived from professional bodies. They might be formal policies or merely have the status of professional guidance—or even simply be wider “trends” that lots of people are noticing and perhaps where there is some impetus for practitioners to respond. It is a good idea, in my view, to immediately take an appropriately critical stance towards the policy area in question, perhaps framing it as a set of assumptions that might be investigated using empirical work or even flatly disagreeing with it. Potentially, you might *believe* in some policy and be trying to investigate or overcome implementation problems. Citing policy documentation can be one useful way of rendering general statements about policy concrete.
- *The practices that you will be investigating.* This might be done by drawing on some institutional documentation, by relating some examples that you have encountered or participated in yourself, and/or by drawing on published literature. The aim would be to illustrate to the reader in quite a concrete sense the kinds of things that you are seeking to investigate. You might well be investigating practice change, or the role of particular tools (such as technologies) within practices. In either case, you should aim to provide an accessible overview of those issues as possible. The balance between *too much* and *not enough* detail can be difficult to judge. In my view, there is a necessity to provide the reader of the Confirmation Document with enough detail to understand the work you are proposing, but without venturing into every detail. In some cases, images such as screenshots might well be helpful in providing some illustration to the reader. Such images are useful

² The relationship between the use of literature in your *Introduction* and the more formal *Literature Review* section is not straightforward and there are different views prominent within the field. See <http://patthomson.net/2015/08/02/literature-work-in-a-journal-article-the-introduction/> for more discussion of this matter.

because they do not, of course, contribute towards the word count of the document; on the other hand, there is a necessity to provide clear Figure labels and to explain the purpose of the Figure in the text, all of which *certainly* does count.

- *Your own background and motivation.* In many cases it is useful to say something informal about what motivates you, personally, to carry out the work. Why are you interested in this topic in particular? For example, you might highlight your own background, experience, and professional expertise. You might also highlight your interest in, or knowledge of, particular areas of research literature or policy. As with all areas of the Confirmation Document, it will be important to restrict the word count expended in discussing this matter—in my experience of reading Confirmation Documents, this is one area where it is tempting to either not discuss the matter *at all*, or to provide *too much* information. A well-written paragraph early in the flow of the document might well suffice. Considering the task of writing this material also seems to sharply pose the following question: should I write in the first person, or not? As a supervisor I have *no preference*, although in my view it is *usually*³ necessary to write in one consistent tense, person and style throughout any document.

When writing about these issues, a number of decisions will have to be made. There will certainly need to be a decision about how many sub-section headings to include. It would be possible, for example, to write the Introduction as a sequence of paragraphs with no subsection headings, or to include several subheadings. It is difficult to make a blanket recommendation about these issues in advance, and so I may well need to comment on this issue in the concrete, when I make comments on your draft submission. One point of discussion that often will merit a sub-heading, however, is the presentation of the research questions. I consider this matter separately below.

3.2 Research questions

The topic of research questions consumes acres of pages across legion research books⁴. There are many ways to approach writing and presenting research questions, so I shall simply try to illustrate how I approach the issue.

Firstly, my RQs are always actually questions; they are *not* statements of interest and they *do* have a question mark at the end.

Secondly, my RQs are explicitly numbered (as RQ1, RQ2, etc.).

Thirdly, my RQs are often organised into a hierarchy, with main questions (like RQ1) supported by sub-question (like RQ1.1, RQ1.2). The main questions are *clear* but might be relatively general, whereas the sub-questions rely on the context of their respective main question for some of their meaning but are much more specific. The aim is to imply that by answering the sub-questions I can effectively answer the attendant main question.

Fourthly, by *clear* questions I mean to say that—to the maximum extent possible—my questions *minimise specialist terminology* and *can be read separately from the surrounding text*.

³ The qualifier *usually* indicates that exceptions certainly exist; an obvious one might be where particular forms of autoethnography are being used. Angela Thody's (2006) book *Writing and Presenting Research*, available via MyiLibrary, considers the issue of different writing voices. Thody herself deliberately varies her writing voice in different sections so as to illustrate particular points. Pat Thomson has repeatedly reflected on this issue on her blog: <http://patthomson.net/2013/07/25/should-i-write-as-an-i/> ; <http://patthomson.net/2013/08/12/more-on-writing-as-i/> ; <http://patthomson.net/2013/08/22/writing-with-i-is-subjective-and-thats-ok/>

⁴ Since I am aware of a minor trend of pointing to Pat Thomson's blog within this document, I shall illustrate this point by saying that Thomson has authored at least four posts on this topic that might prove useful for aiding your thinking: <http://patthomson.net/2011/12/27/what-do-research-questions-want/> ; <http://patthomson.net/2013/10/03/getting-research-questions-wrong-then-right/> ; <http://patthomson.net/2013/12/30/revisiting-the-construction-of-research-questions-a-useful-holiday-read/> ; <http://patthomson.net/2014/09/08/thinking-about-research-questions/>

Fifthly, I need to ensure that my questions are answerable. One way you can do this is to think about what data you will actually have access to within your project. For example, if your project is to be based around semi-structured interviews, it might be useful to formulate RQs that refer *directly* to “beliefs” or “perceptions” or “experiences”—ideally, the perceptions of some *named* group of people, about some *named* issue, within some *named* context. Some research approaches are associated with particular questions. If I see RQs referring to something like the “commonality and variation within the collective perceptions of some *named* phenomenon by some *named* group of people”, for example, then it is clear to me straight away that I am about to read a proposal for a project that uses phenomenography.

Sixthly, I nearly always present my RQs towards the end of my Introduction section.

The point of interaction between the third and fifth points is that sub-questions are directly answerable, whereas main questions might be either directly answerable or answerable as a result of answering the attendant sub-questions.

Some writers pose hard limits on the number of research questions. To some extent, I would concur: you should not pose more questions than you can answer; you should not pose so many questions that the meaning of the project becomes obscured to the reader; and you should not create a rod for your own back out of the sheer number of RQs you will need to address. On the other hand, I have seen examples of projects where three main RQs are each divided into three sub-questions (meaning 12 questions are posed overall), where clarity has been achieved. So I find “rules” about not having more than, say, three RQs difficult to justify.

RQ2. How does empirical research published in Higher Education journals make use of Activity Theory?

RQ2.1. What methodologies are used alongside Activity Theory?

RQ2.2. What data collection methods are used alongside Activity Theory?

RQ2.3. Which concepts from within Activity Theory are highlighted within research analysis as presented?

Figure 3: An example of RQs. Part of an RQ hierarchy for a current desk-based research project.

In case the preceding discussion is difficult to understand in the abstract, I have provided some example RQs of my own from a current project in Fig. 3.

3.3 Section ordering and signposting

In my view it is useful to finish off the Introduction section by indicating to the reader what the structure of the rest of the document will look like. The purpose of doing so is *really* not so much about the document *per se*; it is actually about illustrating the *argumentational structure* that will be deployed within the document. It is important that readers understand not just the content of the sentences they are reading at any given moment, but the purpose of those sentences within the overall narrative. One way of aiding the reader's understanding is by setting out the structure in advance, using what I shall refer to as *signposting*. At this point—at the end of the Introduction—I find it useful to signpost the remainder of the document at a relatively general level, mostly by taking into account the top-level section headings and explaining the purpose of each attendant section. Signposting will also be a useful mechanism at the start of sections, where the structure of the sub-sections can be explained, and at the end of sections, where a brief reference to the next section might be made.

Writing the signposting text does, of course, presuppose that you have come to some sort of decision about the order in which you will present the sections of your Confirmation Document. I shall suggest a rough order in what follows, but you may choose to vary that order or even to increase or reduce the number of sections. It is plausible that you may change your mind about the section order during the course of drafting the document, but doing so comes at a cost in terms of the time taken to re-draft the document. What you should bear in mind is that it is relatively less taxing for a reader when you refer backwards, and relatively more taxing when you refer forwards; moreover, you can assume a

certain degree of reader familiarity with your earlier narrative that cannot be assumed for the subsequent narrative. For example, a reader who is currently reading section 4.5 might be expected to remember what was in section 4.4, and to some (slightly lesser) extent to recall what was in section 2; they would *not*, however, be expected to know what is in section 6. You might assume their recollection of the immediately preceding narrative; similarly, you might assume their recollection of much earlier narrative in some cases and remind them of a point of particular importance in others (a *callback*, e.g., “As I argued in the *Literature Review*...”). Yet the case where more detail will be provided later will *very often* require a *callforward* (e.g., “as will be argued in section 6.2”), and it should be assumed that *callforwards* are often more confusing to readers than *callbacks*. You therefore need to think about how to build your narrative cumulatively, so that the number of *callbacks* is kept to a reasonable number and the number of *callforwards* is kept to the absolute minimum possible.

While this point is a useful general principle, a particularly common instantiation within a Confirmation Document concerns this question: should the *Theoretical Framework* section or the *Literature Review* section come first? In what follows in this guidance document, I shall be assuming that the Literature Review will come first, because this is the most common format and has the advantage of moving the Theoretical Framework and Methodology section closer together; this means that the theory ought still to be clear in the mind of the reader when they read the methodology, thereby allowing an easier evaluation of their alignment. However, in particularly theory-driven projects you may need to move the Theoretical Framework section forward, and doing so will be vital if you will be *using* the theory to evaluate the literature in the Literature Review section. Decisions like these will recur throughout academic writing tasks, and the Confirmation Document is a good place to practice mapping out extended arguments in advance of the more significant challenge to come—the thesis document.

4 Literature Review section

Writing a literature review is also an undertaking that has been written about many times and by many authors. The aim of this guidance is not to replicate the vast amount of information already out there, but instead to set out what a Literature Review section for a *Confirmation Document* might look like. This is a more modest yet more particular section than you will be writing for your PhD thesis document later on. Recall that the purpose of this document is to *set out and justify* a research plan. The literature review section should be aligned with that purpose, and for that reason should aim to provide the location for your project within a wider field of enquiry, and to justify why your project might add to that field. In order to do so, it is necessary to understand that *both* component words of the term “literature review” are supposed to be interpreted actively: if the section does not draw on *literature*, then it is not a literature review; yet if it does not *review* that literature, then it is also not a literature review!

I tend to adopt the position—that many others may well *disagree* with—that the purpose of a Literature Review is to review empirical literature, i.e., work that generates and analyses evidence of some kind. For me, the place to consider theories and “critical reflection” pieces is in the Theoretical Framework section. The fact that I see these sections as quite starkly different is partly what necessitates careful consideration of their order within the document, as discussed in section 3.3. If I am going to undertake some research on University Learning Spaces using Activity Theory, for example, then this Literature Review section might review *previous empirical work* on Learning Spaces; Activity Theory would be mainly considered in the Theoretical Framework section.

In my view, the things that you ought to present within your Literature Review section can be encapsulated by the following bullet-points:

- A *brief introductory paragraph* that signposts the remainder of the section and in particular the various sub-sections that will be encountered (see section 3.3 on signposting);
- A *very brief discussion* stating which “proximate topics” will be reviewed in the section and why those have been

selected from the range of alternatives. Notwithstanding the occasionally heard claim to be researching a “completely new area”, it is always, always, *always* the case that relevant literature exists that can underpin your project. The difference between projects lies in *how far* from the ostensible topic you have to stray to find it (i.e., “*how proximate*” the fields are to your own project). In my view it is useful to formulate your project as being positioned at the intersection between several fields of enquiry—indeed, it may be a reasonable idea to illustrate this point with a simple Venn diagram showing the overlap, with your own project displayed as being at the intersection. For my own PhD project I located three proximate fields, meaning that, for the purposes of the Venn diagram, my project would be labelled as being the grey area in Fig 4.

- *A statement about which proximate topics were considered for inclusion but eventually not selected for review.* It is useful to emphasise that you have carefully considered alternative ways in which your project might be conceived. For example, if you are undertaking a project about learners choosing to register for online learning courses in a particular geographic location, you might to consider proximate fields such as: research into online learner identities; research into developments in institutional online learning provision; research into educational provision in the geographic area in question; research into human motivation and decision-making; etc. I do suggest that no more than three proximate areas be reviewed, and so you will need to prioritise and justify which areas were *included* and *excluded*.
- *A brief description of how you found the literature you will be reviewing.* Chapter 4 of Petticrew & Roberts (2008)⁵, available via MyiLibrary, considers this issue in some depth. For present purposes, if we assume that you will try some search strategy then you might discuss which search engines you used, which search terms you deployed, how you prioritised and filtered papers, and what your priorities are for critiquing the papers (i.e., what you are looking for in them).

Figure 4: Example of a Venn diagram with three overlapping sets and a central intersection.

- *A subsection devoted to each proximate area of enquiry.* These sections should constitute the bulk of the wordcount for your Literature Review section, and these subsections are where the word *review* needs to be particularly active.
 - You should aim to make your own position clear about other work when discussing it—commenting on the strength or appropriateness of others authors' methodology or data, saying whether you think their conclusions would appear to be applicable to your study setting, highlighting why their work is not sufficient to address your research questions, and so on.

⁵ Petticrew, M., & Roberts, H. (2008). *Systematic reviews in the social sciences: A practical guide*. Malden, MA: Blackwell.

- Clearly, offering critique is more difficult, and uses more words, than simply providing a short summary of what the paper says; nonetheless, doing so remains necessary. Some papers—especially those that will influence your work heavily in one way or another—will need to be critiqued in more detail than others. In other cases, you might cluster several papers together and offer your viewpoint on the whole cluster. But “saving words” should not be an excuse to exorcise critique. Indeed, given a straight choice I would rather see *fewer papers reviewed thoughtfully* than a greater number of papers summarised in a very bland way. As a rule-of-thumb, I would hope to see *at least one example of critical comment in every paragraph of your literature review*.
- *A short sub-section at the end of the section drawing together the narrative that you have constructed.* You might highlight the key gaps and points of emphasis within the literature from your point of view, for example, and show how these relate to the objectives of your research.

5 Theoretical Framework section

Perhaps the most important comment to be made about the Theoretical Framework section will seem slightly repetitive of what I have said elsewhere, but here goes: the text needs to be *critical* and directly *related to your own prospective project*. The section should *not* mainly consist of re-phrasing some standard text on the theory you have chosen. Instead, it should seek to justify why you chose the theory⁶ for the current project, to set out which alternatives you considered and discarded, and to emphasise how you expect to use the theory in your work.

Let us consider these points in more detail:

- *Why did you choose the theory?* In my view this should be the first point to be addressed within the section, and have a length of 1-2 paragraphs. Potential reasons might be drawn from some combination of: alignment with your ontological and epistemological stance; your awareness of previous, relevant work that has used the theory; how you perceive that the theory might offer something to the problem at hand (e.g., “this theory claims to account for...”); claims that prior work has been limited by using other theoretical frameworks. In any of these instances, providing secondary citations for purposes of justification will certainly be helpful. You will note that this is the first time in this guidance document that I have mentioned *ontology* and *epistemology*. This is not because I believe they are unimportant, but I do believe that many PhD students write about these issues at too great a length, for little gain. If you have strong beliefs about some issues, then this might have been stated in the Introduction where you discuss your personal motivation for undertaking the project; if this is the case, then you might callback to that discussion here. Otherwise, two or three sentences about your stance and the alignment should be sufficient for more typical Confirmation Documents.
- *What other theories did you consider and reject?* In my view, this issue *definitely* needs to be considered, but—unless there is some particular reason for doing so—I would not exceed more than a few sentences discussing this topic. You might want to mention some theories that are commonly used in work on which you are drawing (for example, in the Literature Review). You might want to mention some theories that might seem to offer similar advantages to the one you have chosen. I would suggest mentioning between 2-4 other theories and briefly stating why you rejected them. Hopefully, having already justified the theory you did choose, this

⁶ It is possibly worth mentioning that what counts as a theory can vary between contexts. Malcolm Tight (2012), in Chapter 13 of *Researching Higher Education, 2nd edition*, available via MyiLibrary, highlights how some theories might have grandiose titles (e.g., Activity Theory) while others are simply concepts that have been developed within particular research settings (see pp. 198-199 for a large table of examples). Here I am assuming that you are describing a 'grandiose' theory constituted by many sub-concepts, but if that is not the case then you will simply have to state the concepts that you are using and the place you intend them to assume within your work.

should be a relatively easy task—because those theories ought *not* to have all the advantages that you have claimed, immediately above, for your candidate theory!

- *What is the theory itself?* This might well be the most difficult part of the section, because for many theories the temptation will be to write a lot of text. In part, I suspect that this problem occurs because people—quite understandably—engage in a period of reading about their chosen theory at the point they are writing their Confirmation Document. The temptation thus arises to regurgitate those theoretical texts that have been recently read in great detail while they are still fresh in the mind; indeed, there may well be some value in doing so for your own notes. But for the Confirmation Document what we really need at *this* moment is a short description of the theory at quite a general level, the names of some key thinkers or milestone works that you will be drawing upon within your work, and some citations to which you would wish to direct the interested reader. One (relatively lengthy?) paragraph ought to suffice.
- *Which elements of the theory will you be using most directly and how?* The fact is that many theories are, in fact, constellations of concepts of which there will likely be too many to explain in detail. My suggestion is to conclude the section with some comments on which concepts are most important to you and which you expect to be drawing upon most heavily within your project, doing so without inadvertently implying that those concepts can be thought of in isolation from the wider framework of the theory. You might also note how those concepts are likely to align with aspects of your methodology and methods—a rare, but allowable, *callforward*—for example, by mentioning whether those concepts will influence your choice of study setting, or your design of data gathering instruments. You should also comment on whether you expect to be using the concepts in a relatively deductive or inductive way, by which I mean whether you will code data from the beginning with reference to your concepts (deductive thinking) or code in a more open way (inductive thinking) and consider the concepts afterwards.

Before discussing the Methodology section, it is worth me stating my position on the use of multiple theories together. The fact is that this can be done, and it can be done very productively. You should be aware from the beginning that combining theories does mean extra work in justifying the combination and accounting for their commensurability. Nonetheless, my position remains that many students attempt to combine multiple theories because of some mistaken impression that adding more theories will automatically lead to a stronger project. (This is a similar misconception to the “adding more methods” temptation that some people also experience). I believe this position to be profoundly mistaken; research theory is not an exercise in baking where the addition of “a bit more salt” will change a poor decision into an acceptable one. In my view, using one theory well allows for easier achievement of coherency and also the opportunity for discussion of the limits of the theory within your thesis. If you wish to use more than one theory, then there should be a *specific* reason for doing so that you can state very briefly and clearly. Otherwise, my advice is to avoid the temptation.

6 Methodology, research design and methods sections⁷

Methodology and *research design* should be clearly differentiated from *methods*, which can be thought about as data collection approaches. To emphasise the differentiation, I suggest that they be separated to some extent in your

⁷ At the time of writing I supervise Part Two students from three different doctoral programmes in the Department—“Educational Research (Higher Education)”; “Higher Education Research, Enhancement and Evaluation”; and “Technology Enhanced Learning”—and yet my intention is only to create one version of this document. Students on the Educational Research (Higher Education) programme will have different requirements here from those on the other two programmes; the word limit for the EdRes(HE) Confirmation Document is slightly shorter, because on that programme the Methodology and methods need to be set out in a different document and are evaluated separately, within Modules A and C.

Confirmation Document. Whether this means having entirely separate sections, which is the way this guidance document is written, or whether headings at the sub-section level should be considered sufficient, is a matter that is really up to you to decide in the end. Let us consider what Methodology means with reference, once again, to Pat Thomson's blog:

I understand methodology to be theory; it's theory about the research methods that will be used. It's theory which underpins the decisions made about the researcher's range of choices of – for example – what to study; who to study; where to study; which research tradition to work within; what knowledges to draw on; what to include and exclude, foreground and background and the consequences of this decision; what counts as data and why; relational and ethical concerns; and how to represent the findings/how to write the research.

<http://patthomson.net/2013/02/18/methodology-isnt-methods-or-what-goes-in-a-methods-chapter/>

What should be clear from this quotation is that methodology indicates the documentation, with justification, of high-level project decisions, whereas methods refers to much lower-level data gathering issues, including the design of instruments. For some writers—including Thomson—there seems to be a level in-between methodology and methods, called *research design*, where:

a research design is the way that the researcher assembles and sequences the tools, and the ways in which these are applied, according to the principles elaborated through the methodological choices

I see methods as the 'tools' that are used to do the research

both from: <http://patthomson.net/2013/02/18/methodology-isnt-methods-or-what-goes-in-a-methods-chapter/>

Speaking for myself, I am not particularly enthusiastic about pedantically defining where the the boundaries between these concepts lie in a universalistic way; the way in which you document your research might be slightly different dependent upon the nature of the design itself. So long as the design is logically documented in a way that moves in some sense from high to medium to low-level design issues (and I do prefer to move in that order, *from high to low*) and takes into account what your readers might be expected to understand in advance, then you ought to be on safe ground.

As before, there are many approaches to writing a methodology review already documented in the literature. One example can be found in Angela Thody's (2006) book *Writing and Presenting Research*, which I have already recommended earlier in the document. Box 7.3, on pp. 99-101 of Thody's book, provides a useful list of the things you ought to consider. One immediate point to note is that Thody recommends considering your research paradigm—your epistemological and ontological stances, basically—early on in the methodology review. In my view, where this needs to be discussed depends on your sequence of sections. If your Theoretical Framework section comes before the Methodology, as I am suggesting in this guidance, then my advice is to position that discussion within *that* section rather than within this one. In general, it is my view that the paradigmatic discussion should occur early—because, within your exposition, other decisions, such as those about theory and methodology, should arise from that discussion.

To illustrate the *sort* of thread of thinking I hope you will arrive at, I shall enumerate an example sequence in this way:

- *What do your research paradigm and theoretical framework imply and what do your empirical opportunities allow?* The fact is that different theoretical frameworks suggest different research approaches. Phenomenography prioritises collective perceptions and so discussions with a number of people about some issue are implied by the framework; cognitive load theory involves measuring perceptions of load *in situ*, perhaps implying an experimental scenario and an instrument that can be used to build a numeric scale. Some theoretical frameworks might imply longitudinal work, or case studies of some particular kind, or surveys, or some sort of observation, etc. In all cases, you will have to build a project that you can actually do within

constraints of time, resources, institutional rules, ethics⁸, and so on. Discussing these issues is usually the best place to start.

- *What kind of research methodology will you therefore deploy?* Examples might include particular forms of case study, survey, ethnography, action research, design-based research, Change Laboratory, desk-based research, randomised controlled trial, experiment or quasi-experiment, mixed-methods, phenomenography, phenomenology, narrative or autobiographical methodology, etc. Discuss what the main features of that form of methodology are, and how they align with your theoretical framework and research objectives. You may need to name a particular form of methodology (there are several types of case study, for example), and will usually indicate one or more key texts that have informed your thinking about this matter.
 - You will need to think carefully about your *sampling strategy*—who will be your participants, why have you selected them, and how many do you need? I would usually be documenting the sampling decisions around this point in the exposition, but the further separation and indentation of this bullet-point is meant to suggest that where you discuss sampling might well vary between different Confirmation Documents. Sampling ought to be discussed in most methodological texts—your task is to name the form of sampling, state why it fits your methodology and aims, and briefly discuss the sampling for your project. It is usually a good idea to be *specific*: “In this project I will seek to recruit *x* students from discipline *A* in one university, together with *y* academics from discipline *A*”.
- *What research design will you use?* By this point in the exposition you need to have formalized the methodology and be moving on to more precise decisions about methods. Examples of methods might include semi-structured interviews, document analysis, questionnaires, participant observation, and so on. If you are using only one method then you will need to specify how that method fits with your methodology and how it will provide you with information that can be analysed to answer your research questions. If you are using several methods then you will still need to explain those things, but you will also need to explain how the different methods have been *integrated* so that the project remains coherent. Robert Yin has discussed this issue within the context of mixed-method design⁹, where he suggests that it is necessary to align different methods by considering their relationships to research questions, their units of analysis, their study samples, their instrumentation and the attendant analytic strategies. One useful point made by Yin is that “mixed-methods research” should not merely be thought of as that which uses methods on either side of some imaginary dividing line between “quantitative” and “qualitative”, but as any research that deploys disparate research instruments. My suggestion is to consider the alignment between your methods using these lenses even if you are not explicitly using “mixed methods” as your methodology.
- *What can you say about the design of each of your instruments?* It may be too early for you to provide the likes of your interview protocols and/or questionnaire designs—and the word count allowance would probably not allow you to document your project to that level of detail in any case—but it ought to be possible to say something about how you will design those instruments. If you are planning to use semi-structured interviews, for example, then you might wish to consider what kinds of questions you would ask and how you would run the interviews as events¹⁰. If you will be deploying a questionnaire, then you might consider what kinds of

⁸ You will recall from Fig. 1 that research ethics is *not* usually considered at any length in the Confirmation Document. This is because you will have to complete a separate ethics application, which I recommend you start to draft once you have submitted your Confirmation Document, while you are waiting for comments to come back from the panel.

⁹ Yin, R. K. (2006). Mixed methods research: Are the methods genuinely integrated or merely parallel? *Research in the Schools*, 13(1). Available from: http://web.archive.org/web/20100827031304/http://www.msera.org/Rits_131/Yin_131.pdf

¹⁰ Glynis Cousin's book, available via MyiLibrary, provides useful and practical guidance on a variety of research methods. The range of methods covered is mainly qualitative, and includes consideration of semi-structured interview and focus

questions will you use (open-ended, Likert-scale). In each case, it will be useful to say something about the relationships between your methods and your research questions.

- *What limitations (might) exist in your project design?* In particular, I would advise you to consider:
 - What *potential* limitations exist that *are practically avoidable*, and what steps you will take to minimise the effects of those limitations in practice.
 - What *apparent* limitations others might perceive in your work that you do not believe are limitations. Such discrepancies might arise, for example, because of differences between the epistemological positions of the author and some segments of the potential readership.
 - What *unavoidable* limitations exist. All research projects do have limitations; how will you acknowledge those and avoid overgeneralising when making claims in your subsequent writing?

7 Endpieces

Four more sections should be present at the end of the document, in my view, in some cases simply because Confirmation panels expect them: a Conclusion, a Timetable (or Plan of Action), a proposed Thesis Structure, and the References. Although each of them probably only requires a few words by way of explanation, I shall consider each in turn below.

7.1 Conclusion

This section needs to retrace the argument of your project clearly, but briefly. The kinds of issues that should be mentioned are as follows: What is the context of your research in terms of research field, policy and practice? What questions will you pursue within that context? What theoretical approach will be taken, and why is this apposite? What methodology and methods will you use, and why do you think that these can provide the kind of insight that is needed? In particular, *potentially devoting more time to it within this section than to the other questions combined*, you should aim to address the following question: What does your research hope to contribute to that context (particularly to the research field)?

7.2 Timetable

The Timetable, or Project Plan, or Plan of Action, is something that I advise you to include mainly on the grounds that many panel reviewers will complain if you do not. My own enthusiasm here is fairly limited, but since you will be doing the work of creating the timetable I advise you to take the opportunity for reflection. The format of the timetable could be a Gantt chart or a Table of tasks ordered by time period. My suggestion is that you map your tasks down to the *level of calendar months*. As a minimum, you should consider practicalities (such as obtaining and analysing data), and writing tasks (such as writing each chapter, and revising the whole thesis later on). You might also consider specifying those time periods where your own workload might prevent much progress, or where participants will be accessible to you. In general, it is a good idea to set out the timetable for a period of 24 months¹¹. With regard to writing, you should consider which chapters you might write first and at what points within the 24 month time period you are likely to have time to write. I do *not* recommend writing only at the end of the project, and I do *not* recommend writing the chapters in

group design that focusses on *managing the event*; Cousin also provides a dedicated chapter for those using interviews within phenomenography.

Cousin, G. (2009). *Researching learning in higher education: An introduction to contemporary methods and approaches*. Oxon: Routledge.

¹¹ If you are a student on the Technology Enhanced Learning programme, setting out a timetable having a duration of 24 months is *de facto* compulsory. (If your project has any other timescale, then in my experience the panel definitely *will* ask you to amend it to become 24 months exactly.)

numeric order (in fact, I actually *did* write the chapters of my own thesis in numeric order, and in retrospect I consider that doing so was an error; I would usually advise writing the Methodology chapter first, as early as you can within the project timeline).

7.3 Thesis structure

Typically, it is a requirement to provide an outline of the chapter titles for your proposed thesis document, along with a potential wordcount in each case¹². For those chapters where it is possible, you might break the chapter down and name the main section titles. It is not usually necessary to specify word counts for the sections. The total wordcount for the proposed thesis document should meet the wordcount limits set out by the programme (usually 50,000 words).

7.4 References

This section should not really require explanation. My only comments would be: firstly, please use a consistent style throughout the section (when I am a panel member, I see a lot of Confirmation Documents with references in different styles, apparently simply pasted together, at which point I always ask for the section to be tidied up prior to acceptance); secondly, please ensure that any URLs you provide can be accessed without login credentials. Typically, materials you cite should be publicly accessible, which is why Technical Reports are only added as references if they are published external to the organisation, why private correspondence can be cited in the body text but does not require an attendant reference, and why, for example, books accessed online behind institutional firewalls should be cited simply *as books*, not as online resources.

8 This document

- 1.0 Version 1.0 of this document was prepared 10-13 August 2015.
- 1.1 Version 1.1, prepared 10 September 2015. A moderate number of typos were removed and a small number of sentences amended.
- 1.2 Version 1.2, prepared 10 May 2018. No text has been altered, but the accessibility of the document has been improved.

Please do send comments on this document to me. I would very much like to iteratively improve it based on your comments.

¹² The word counts you suggest here are, it should go without saying, *not* binding!